

DYNAMIC PROPERTIES OF THERMAL CURING FIBER/EPOXY SUPPORTING BOOM

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ABSTRACT

Utilizing different material properties of thermal curing matrix lower and higher than glass transition temperature (T_g), a kind of Kevlar fiber reinforced E51 epoxy composite material was fabricated and inflatable deployable supporting booms were made. Electrical resistant wire was used to control temperature of thermal set matrix, and an enclosed Kapton membrane was used for inflation to control the final shape of booms. The effects of temperature and inner pressure on the dynamic of supporting cantilever booms were investigated through experimental modal analysis. Results shows that add inner gas pressure, proportion of matrix increase natural frequency of supporting boom. Natural frequency is sensitive to temperature, when increase matrix temperature, structural natural frequency decrease. Finally, the relationships between natural frequencies with inner gas pressure and around glass transition temperature were obtained by poly fitting to guide engineering design of inflatable deployable space structure.

1 INTRODUCTION

Future large space structures will require deployable structures with high stiffness, high stability, and compact stowage. Inflatable space structures have long been acknowledged as a means of reducing complexity, weight, volume, and cost of large space systems. Heat curing deployable booms is a basic supporting part of space inflatable structures, the space inflatable deployment process as an important stage in its function. The rigidizable inflatable get-away-special experiment was run successfully on board STS-123 (Endeavor) in March 2008. Brett J. Cooper et al. measure the structural characteristics, the deployment pressure, temperature and modal response [1]. A microsatellite which carried an inflatable gravity-gradient boom was launched into orbit successfully in November 2012. After being stored on-orbit for 6 months, the inflatable method was applied to the inflatable boom to unfold the 2.0 kg tip mass steadily at a distance 3.0 m away from the microsatellite in May 2013[2]. Griffith and Main [3] and Park [4] performed experimental investigation into the dynamics of an inflated torus. Smalley and Tinker [5] have studied the dynamic behavior of an inflated beam. They have modeled the effect of the enclosed fluid by adding non-structural mass to the shell elements. Srivastava [6] developed a realistic model, and dynamic interaction between the enclosed fluid and the torus has been included. It is concluded that fluid-structure interaction significantly affects the dynamic behavior of inflatable space structures. Main et al. wrote a very significant paper describing results of modal tests of inflated cantilever beams and the determination of effective material properties [7]. Changes in material properties for different pressures were also discussed, and the beam model was used in a more complex structure. The paper demonstrated that conventional finite element analysis packages could be very useful in the analysis of complex inflatable structures. References [8, 9, 10] describe closed-form and finite element beam representations of inflatable cylinder dynamics, along with shell element models for comparison.

In this paper, the thermal curing fabric composite support boom as the research object, the modal testing method of single point excitation and multi-point response were studied in different

temperature and different pressure of different geometric effects of the dynamic performance of the support boom.

2 DYNAMIC TESTING METHODS

In this paper, the structural dynamics characteristics of the thermal curing Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom after aerated expansion are analyzed experimentally via the DEWE801 vibration test system. Along the boom length, four three-axis sensors(PCB35A16) are evenly arranged in the equidistant, then obtaining the dynamic characteristics of the thermal set Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom by the excitation of the force hammer, the entire test system is shown in Fig. 1 Using the same method, the structural natural frequencies of the boom are tested and analyzed which possesses different inflation pressure, temperature, resin content, number of layers, length of inflatable boom and cross-sectional diameter, in order to obtain the effects of inflation pressure, temperature change, resin content on the structural natural frequencies of the thermal curing Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom.

Fig. 1 Dynamic test system diagram

According to the test scheme, the dynamic test system is shown in Fig. 2, including the DEWE-801 vibration tester, KIMO-CP-200 pressure gauge, inflatable pump, VarioCAM infrared thermometer, and the thermal curing Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom, Vibration measurement sensors and other components. During the test, the measurement channel is selected first and the sensitivity coefficient of the sensor is set, then the stimulation is carried out by the force hammer, and the structural natural frequencies as well as the corresponding damping are selected by modal test method. Finally, the corresponding structural natural frequencies of each order are selected according to the finite element simulation vibration mode.

Fig. 2 Testing system device connection

3 RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

3.1 Influence of Inflation Pressure on Dynamic Characteristics

In this paper, the testing object is a single layer thermal set Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom whose resin content is 50%, and T_g temperature is 45° C. Firstly, the thermal set Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom was heated to a T_g temperature of 45°C; Secondly, testing the dynamic properties of the thermal set boom under the conditions of 0kPa, 20kPa, 30kPa, 40kPa, 50kPa, 60kPa, 70kPa, 80kPa and 90kPa, respectively. The single-point excitation multi-point response test method is used to obtain the BODE diagram, the vibration pattern picture and the admittance circle analysis figure of the first-order natural frequency of the thermal curing fiber/Epoxy support boom when the charge pressure on the inner surface of the support boom is 0kPa, 20kPa, 40kPa and 60kPa, respectively. When the support boom's internal pressure is 0ka, under the state of 1.0m cantilever beam boundary conditions, combined with BODE diagram shown in Fig. 3, and admittance circle as shown in Fig. 4, they indicate that the first-order natural frequency is 11.58Hz, the structural modal damping ratio is 0.025, respectively.

Fig. 3 45 ° C, 0kPa modal amplitude frequency function curve

Fig. 4 The first mode admittance circle at 45°C, 0kPa

In the same method, under the same conditions, it can be drawn from the figure that the first-order natural frequency of the thermal set Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom is 11.9Hz When its internal pressure is 20kPa; the first-order natural frequency does not change when its internal pressure increase to 30kPa; When its internal pressure is 40kPa, the first-order natural frequency rises to 12.1Hz; and the first-order natural frequency does not change until the internal pressure is up to 90kPa, the first-order natural frequency reaches to 12.3Hz

The first-order natural frequencies at 0kPa, 20kPa, 30kPa, 40kPa, 50kPa, 60kPa, 70kPa, 80kPa, and 90kPa, respectively, were compared in order to study the effect of the internal surface inflation pressure on the dynamic properties of the thermal set Kevlar fiber/Epoxy support boom at the T_g temperature. The data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Dynamic Characteristics under Different Inflation Pressure

inner pressure(kPa)	First-order natural frequency
0	11.7

10kPa increased 9 times to 90kPa, the structure of the first-order natural frequency increased by only 5.13%.

3.2 Influence of Tg temperature on Dynamic Characteristics

When testing curing degree was influenced by the dynamic characteristics of the support boom, an inflation pressure of 20kPa was applied to the inner surface. When the same charge pressure is maintained, the boom is heated by a DC voltage of 255 V and the temperature is monitored by the VarioCAM infrared thermometer. The temperature diagram of the boom wall is shown in Fig. 10. It can be seen that the resistance wire with an interval of 20mm achieves uniform heating of the structure. Figure a, b, c, d is 25 °C, 45 °C, 65 °C, 85 °C temperature nephogram respectively.

Fig. 7 The nephogram at different temperature

Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show that the first frequency of the support boom is 18.371 Hz and the second frequency is 142.8Hz. The modal damping ratios are 0.155 and 0.135, and the average modal damping ratio is 0.145.

Fig. 8 The amplitude frequency function curve at 25°C

Fig. 9 The first mode and the second mode admittance circle at 25°C

In this paper the first frequency changes to 15.876Hz and the second gets 115.17Hz at 45°C. The modal damping ratios are 0.266 and 0.07, and the average modal damping ratio is 0.1685. The first frequency changes to 12.794Hz and the second gets 90.522Hz at 65°C. The modal damping ratios are 0.217 and 0.05, and the average modal damping ratio is 0.134 (Fig. 10). The first frequency gets 10.933Hz and the second gets 81.406Hz at 85°C. The modal damping ratios are 0.268 and 0.03, and the average modal damping ratio is 0.15. To study the effect of temperature to the inflatable support boom's dynamic characteristics, the first frequency and the second frequency change are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 10 The amplitude frequency function curve at 65°C

Table 2 the dynamic characteristics of supporting boom at different temperature

Temperature	The first frequency/Hz	The second frequency /Hz
25°C	18.37	142.80
45°C	15.88	115.17
65°C	12.79	90.52
85°C	10.93	81.41

Based on the database in the table 2, we can see that the temperature gets higher, the first frequency and the second frequency of the support boom gets lower from the Fig. 11. Compared with 25°C the first frequency of support boom reduces 13.58% and the second frequency reduces 19.35% at 45°C; the first frequency of support boom reduces 30.36% and the second frequency reduces 36.61% at 65°C; the first frequency of support boom reduces 40.49% and the second frequency reduces 43.00% at 85°C from Table 3.

Fig. 11 The effect of temperature to the support boom's support boom

Table 3 The effect of temperature to dynamic characteristics of support boom

Temperature	The first frequency's change rate	The second frequency's change rate
25C°	-	-
45C°	-13.58%	-19.35%
65C°	-30.36%	-36.61%
85C°	-40.49%	-43.00%

9 CONCLUSIONS

A kind of Kevlar fiber reinforced E51 epoxy composite material was fabricated and inflatable deployable self-support booms were made. Electrical resistant wire was used to control temperature of thermal set matrix, and an enclosed Kapton membrane was used for inflation to control the final shape of booms. Results shows that add inner gas pressure, proportion of matrix increase natural frequency of supporting boom. Natural frequency is sensitive to temperature, when increase matrix temperature, structural natural frequency decrease. Finally, the relationships between natural frequencies with inner gas pressure and around glass transition temperature were obtained by poly fitting to guide engineering design of inflatable deployable space structure.

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